

Managing challenging waste fractions: Mechanical recycling of router housings from WEEE and environmental assessment

Yasemin Celik*, Meret Jürgens, Niklas Rode, Madina Shamsuyeva, Hans-Josef Endres

IKK – Institute of Plastics and Circular Economy, Leibniz Universität Hannover, An der Universität 2, 30823 Garbsen, Germany

*Corresponding author. *E-mail address:* celik@ikk.uni-hannover.de

Article type

Research Report

ORCID IDs

Yasemin Celik (0000-0003-3104-0868), Meret Jürgens (0009-0006-0593-0030), Niklas Rode (0009-0007-7985-2757), Madina Shamsuyeva (0000-0003-2564-4104), Hans-Josef Endres (0000-0001-8202-3190)

Abstract

Waste streams consisting of various materials pose significant challenges for mechanical recycling processes. Discarded router casings are a relevant example of this, as they are typically processed via conventional waste electrical and electronic equipment (WEEE) recycling channels, which often involve the energy recovery of mixed plastic fractions. This study assesses both the technical feasibility and the environmental sustainability of the mechanical recycling of real router casings. A recycling process was developed comprising pre-shredding, shredding, pelletisation and extrusion to produce an acrylonitrile-butadiene-styrene and polycarbonate (ABS/PC) recyclate. The material was compared with commercially available recyclates of the same polymer type in terms of melt flow rate and mechanical properties, including tensile strength, tensile modulus and impact strength. The results show that the recycled material exhibits suitable melt flow properties and comparable or improved mechanical performance. Furthermore, a life cycle assessment (LCA) was carried out to compare the environmental impacts of the proposed recycling process with conventional treatment routes, such as incineration with energy recovery. Whilst conventional treatment methods may have a lower net impact due to energy credits, mechanical recycling can achieve a negative net environmental impact if the recycled material replaces virgin polypropylene in suitable applications. Overall, the results demonstrate the technical feasibility and environmental potential of recycling router housings, but also highlight limitations regarding the variability of product design, data availability and the transferability of the approach to other plastic fractions from waste electrical and electronic equipment.

Keywords

WEEE; plastics; mechanical recycling; router housings; ABS/PC; recyclate; life cycle assessment (LCA)

1. Introduction

Currently, most post-consumer plastic recyclates come from packaging recycling, which is characterised by established legal frameworks and mature collection and logistics systems. For other plastic waste streams, particularly from technical and medical applications, there are currently few functioning circular solutions [1]. However, a functioning circular economy beyond the packaging sector is essential for the future-oriented resilient and sustainable use of plastics. In addition to recycling-friendly design ('design for recycling'), this requires further development of mechanical recycling technologies and targeted material and product design that enables the use of high-quality recyclates and multiple recycling ('design for recyclates') [2]. At the same time, input streams from technical applications that have hardly been used to date must be tapped and the quality of the resulting recyclates significantly improved. The material recycling of plastics from WEEE poses a particular challenge in this context due to the high diversity of polymers and the steadily increasing use of different additives. The aim of this study is to determine the effectiveness of different pre-treatment and recycling strategies in terms of their suitability for separating, mechanical recycling and thus returning a fraction of WEEE components to the polymer cycle. The study aims to achieve the highest possible quality of mechanical recycling of an ABS or PC/ABS fraction.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Materials

The WEEE components treated in this paper originate from the real waste collection of router housings from a large and extensive corporation at a WEEE waste recycling facility, Electrocyling GmbH. For density separation using the float sink process, salt (sodium chloride) was used to produce a salt solution for adjusting the density of the separation medium. Water was used for the cleaning and separation process. The recyclates used for comparison are Anjacom® PC/ABS R050/75S by almaak international GmbH (Germany) [3] (referred to as 'R1') and Altech PC+ABS ECO 1000/568 by MOCOM Compounds GmbH & Co. KG (Germany) [4] referred to as 'R2').

2.2. Methods

As part of this study, the input material undergoes a multi-stage mechanical pre-treatment and processing route consisting of shredding, separation (magnetic separation and float-sink separation), cleaning, extrusion and subsequent injection moulding (Fig.1). The test procedure is first outlined below and then described in detail in the corresponding subsections. The first step is to inspect and characterise the waste materials in order to determine its composition and initial condition with regard to relevant material-related parameters. Based on this, various recycling pre-treatment strategies and different process sequences were developed and practically investigated. For the most promising process route, an ecological assessment in the form of a life cycle assessment (LCA) is also carried out in order to comprehensively quantify the environmental impact of the process and compare it with alternative treatment strategies.

Figure 1: Processes and nomenclature of the mechanical recycling approach

In an initial step, the router housings are separated from electrical components such as circuit boards and cables and analysed with regard to their main polymer composition. For this purpose, the housing parts are shredded into flakes and a representative sample of 49 randomly selected flakes is examined (Fig.2). Polymer identification is carried out using a Fourier transform infrared (FTIR) microscope (LUMOS II, Bruker Optik GmbH, Germany) operated in ATR mode to identify the polymer types and to derive suitable pre-treatment and density separation parameters based on the input stream composition.

Following density separation, the resulting floating and sinking fractions are again analysed by FTIR to confirm the polymer distribution and to evaluate the effectiveness of the selected separation parameters. Finally, the produced recyclate (granulate) is examined using FTIR to detect potential foreign polymers and to assess the overall separation quality and purity of the material stream. FTIR spectra were recorded using a scan time of 30 scans, in attenuated total reflectance (ATR) mode, over a wavenumber range of 4000–750 cm^{-1} .

Figure 2: Representative sample of 49 randomly selected flakes

2.3. Pre-treatment and mechanical recycling

The samples compared in this study are named based on their technical process and material properties. For easier understanding, Figure 1 shows the samplename and its process.

2.3.1. Shredding and separation

The shredding and separation of impurities like metal or other polymers is an important step in the recycling process. The bulk material delivered, with a grain size exceeding 25 cm, was crushed in a HD 38/54 twin-shaft crusher (JBF, Germany) with a screen size of 8 and 25 mm. Finally, the fractions are fed into a magnetic separator (JBF, Germany) and separated from metallic impurities. The aim of the two grind sizes is to test the influence of the grind sizes on the separation quality of the materials during the density separation process. The following processes are carried out for both grind sizes. An important step was the subsequent float-sink separation, which was initially carried out on a laboratory scale and then scaled up using a centrifugal separator (Circulyzer, Austria) to validate its practical suitability. The Circulyzer is a wet-mechanical processing plant that efficiently washes and separates mixed plastic and waste fractions, in particular using float-sink/centrifugal force technology, to recover plastics for recycling.

In order to obtain a pure separation fraction, the ground materials (S8, S25, F8, F25) previously identified with FTIR are tested for their density in accordance with ISO 1183-1. The separation took place in two consecutive density stages.:

1. First stage (water, density 1.0): Here, the first floating fraction separates. These are polyolefins, which float to the surface due to their lower density. These are no longer considered. The polymers with a higher density sink and the first sinking fraction of ABS and PC is formed (1.0_S8 and 1.0_S25).
2. Second stage (salt water/brine, density 1.1): The material that sank in the first step is transferred to a brine bath. Here, two further fractions are created: The second floating fraction, which, as expected, is ABS (F8 and F25). This material is then fed into the extrusion and final injection moulding process.
3. The third fraction (sink fraction), consisting of ABS/PC and PC (S8 and S25), cannot be fed into a stable extrusion process in the further course of the process.

The float-sink separation with salt water requires the fraction to be rinsed with lukewarm water. This was washed out once in a container while stirring by hand. After the process to remove the salt residues. Subsequently, the floating fraction (ABS) and sinking fraction (PC/ABS) are identified using FTIR (7 samples each at 4 different locations).

2.3.2. Extrusion

The extrusion was carried out at processing temperatures of 285 °C. Extrusion with a double screw Process 16 laboratory extruder (Thermo Fisher Scientific, Germany) under vacuum to remove volatile components. The extruder is a twin-screw extruder with a screw diameter of 16 mm and an L/D ratio of 40:1.

2.4. Characterisation of the recycled plastics

The melt volume rate (MVR) of the regranulates was determined three times according to DIN EN ISO 1133 using an extrusion plastometer MFR/MVR ZwickRoell Aflow (ZwickRoell GmbH & Co. KG, Germany) at 230 °C under 2.16 kg. Test specimens for mechanical testing according to the DIN EN ISO 527-1 (type CW) were produced from the regranulate in an injection moulding machine BOY XS (Dr. Boy GmbH & Co. KG, Germany). Processing was carried out under the usual process parameters for ABS (230 °C). The produced test specimens were then conditioned in accordance with ISO 291 at 23°C for 48 hours. Mechanical characterisation includes tensile testing based on DIN EN ISO 527-2 at room temperature using a ZwickRoell Z030 TEW material testing machine (ZwickRoell GmbH & Co. KG, Germany). Eight samples are tested for each parameter to determine the mean value. Bending tests were performed five times according to DIN EN ISO 178 using the same material testing machine used for the tensile testing. The impact strength test was determined in accordance with ISO 179-2 using a ZwickRoell HIT25P pendulum impact tester (ZwickRoell GmbH & Co. KG, Germany). Ten test specimens with type 1 according to ISO 179-1 were tested for each material.

The thermal properties of the polymer samples derived from WEEE were examined using differential scanning calorimetry by using DIN EN ISO 11357 (DSC). The measurements were performed with a DSC 214 Polyma (NETZSCH, Germany) under a nitrogen atmosphere. Approximately 5–10 mg of material was analysed using dual determination in hermetically sealed aluminium crucibles per measurement. The inorganic content of the WEEE samples was determined based on the combustion residue after a single specific combustion in a muffle furnace at 450°C.

A JEOL JSM-IT510LA scanning electron microscope (SEM) with a Quorum PP3010T cryo-preparation system (JEOL Ltd. / Quorum Technologies Ltd., Japan) equipped with energy dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDX) was used to analyse the ignition residue samples and identify the chemical elements in the samples.

The characterisation results of the PC/ABS recyclates from the router housings were compared to commercially available PC/ABS recyclates for injection moulding application or thermoforming using information from the technical data sheets. The recyclates used for comparison are Anjacom® PC/ABS R050/75S by almaak international GmbH (Germany) [3] (referred to as 'R1') and Altech PC+ABS ECO 1000/568 by MOCOM Compounds GmbH & Co. KG (Germany) [4] (referred to as 'R2').

2.5. Environmental assessment

The environmental impacts were assessed by performing a Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) of the most promising recycling approach and the current waste treatment, incineration with energy recovery. The system boundaries were defined using a 'cut-off' approach from the collected waste to the production of regranulate for injection moulding. For reference, the results of the recycling approach were compared to the impacts of virgin material production and the current waste treatment, incineration with energy recovery. The virgin material to be replaced was modelled as a blend of 65% ABS and 35% PC. As much data as possible was taken from lab-scale and semi-industrial scale plants and was complemented by literature data [5]. Thereby, the process data for the developed mechanical recycling approach was obtained for all processes listed in Table 1. The life cycle inventories for the environmental assessment were prepared using the 'LCA For Experts' software (formerly known as 'GaBi', version 10.9.1.17) and the Managed LCA Database (formerly known as 'GaBi database', version 2025.1). More information on the life cycle inventories and underlying assumptions is provided in the Supplementary Information.

The environmental impacts were calculated using the Environmental Footprint (EF) 3.1 method provided by the European Commission. The results of the 16 assessed environmental impact categories that are covered by the EF 3.1 method were summarized using a normalized and weighted single score with normalisation and weighting factors [6]. For further examination of the influence of the individual data points, a scenario analysis was carried out. In this analysis, the efficiency of float-sink separation was reduced from the industrial base scenario to a laboratory scale in one scenario and further increased to a standardized industrial-scale process in another scenario. Further information on the underlying assumptions is provided in the Supplementary Information.

Table 1: Processes modelled for the mechanical recycling approach; scale indication based on equipment throughput (semi-industrial = low end of industrial throughput)

Process	Equipment name	Data source	Scale
Pre-grinding (2-shaft shredder)	Two-shaft shredder	Collected data	Lab
Magnetic Separator	Magnetic separator (JBF, Germany)	Collected data	Lab
Float-sink-separation (water, salt)	'Circulyzer' separation unit for density separation	Estimated data	Industrial
Washing	-	Literature data	Industrial
Drying	-	Literature data	Industrial
Shredding	25.38s cutting mill (Wanner Technik GmbH, Germany)	Collected data	Lab
Extrusion	Process 16 laboratory extruder (Thermo Fisher Scientific, Germany)	Collected data	Lab
Granulation	-	Dataset	Industrial

3. Results and Discussion

3.1. Characterisation of the input stream and magnetic metal separation

The highest material distribution (Fig. 3) is found in ABS and PC/ABS. ABS is the dominant plastic for housings and components. PC/ABS blends are also frequently used in the E&E sector [7]. However, the polymer proportions in the mixtures can vary, for example, due to the device type, year of manufacture, and production series [8] [9]

Figure 3: Distribution of polymers contained in the sample based on FTIR analysis (ASA (acrylonitrile-styrene-acrylate), MABS (methyl methacrylate-acrylonitrile-butadiene-styrene), PBT (polybutylene terephthalate), PP (polypropylene), EPDM (ethylene-propylene-diene rubber), PUR (polyurethane))

After magnetic separation, 300 g of a 7 kg sample was sorted and removed as magnetic (Fig.1). A further pass indicates that there are no magnetic components in the fraction.

3.2. Separation - Evaluation of the float/sink separation and the extruded granules

The FTIR analyses of the different fractions show clear differences between them. The analyses of the ground material after float/sink separation (F8, F25, S8, S25) can be seen in the Figure 4. Here, clear ABS bands (orange) can be seen in the float fraction (F8, F25). The sink fraction (S8, S25) shows ABS and PC (blue) spectra. (2237 cm^{-1} (nitrile stretching vibration of ABS), 1770 cm^{-1} (C=O stretching vibration of polycarbonate), 1600–1500 cm^{-1} (aromatic C=C stretching vibrations from both plastics), 1230 cm^{-1} (C-O stretching vibration of polycarbonate) [10] The ABS band can also be seen at 700–760 cm^{-1} . [11, 12].)

Figure 4: FTIR results for the a) floating fraction (F8, F25) and b) sinking fraction (S8, S25) at 1,1g/cm³ (orange: ABS spectra, blue: PC spectra). This FTR analysis shows the particle size of 8mm. 25mm gives the same results

While these results provide the expected polymers, a comparison with the granules (G8, G25) reveals differences. Whereas the bulk material of the float fractions (F8, F25) was originally classified as ABS, the FTIR spectra of the granulated material (G8, G25) exhibit typical ABS-PC characteristics (Fig. 5). This discrepancy is likely attributable to reduced separation efficiency, resulting from variations in PC or ABS content and the subsequent impact on material densities within the WEEE stream.

Figure 5 FTIR results for the floating fraction granulate (G8,) (orange: ABS spectra, blue: PC spectra). This FTR analysis shows the particle size of 8mm. 25mm gives the same results

The spectra of the sink fraction (S8, S25) (red curve), which did not result in a stable extrusion process (Fig. 6), show the combined main bands of ABS and PC, which are typical for PC/ABS blends, as mentioned above. However, the typical ABS band at 700–760 cm^{-1} is not pronounced here. This indicates that the sink fraction has a lower ABS content and a higher PC content. In the figure mentioned, the samples were compared using the FTIR library. The blue curve shows typical PC/ABS spectra with a hit quality of 901. The green curve shows a typical PC curve with a hit quality of 867.

Figure 6: Spectra of the sink fraction with FTIR library comparison

The discrepancy between the expected and the actual detected polymer composition can be attributed to the material heterogeneity in WEEE.

In particular, typical additives and varying PC and ABS proportions in WEEE components [13] make it difficult to achieve clear separation on a laboratory scale. As a result, samples of PC or ABS components occasionally appear in

the floating fraction, even though PC/ABS would normally be assigned to the sinking fraction due to its higher density. This may be due to E&E component-specific density variations [14] caused by different material proportions or additives [15]. In addition, float/sink separation in the laboratory has a higher potential for error compared to industrial processes. Lower process stability – for example, due to tiny particles remaining on the water surface, varying flow conditions, uneven sinking times, or contamination altering the density of the separation medium – can significantly impair the separation quality [14].

Overall, the results show that FTIR spectroscopy allows reliable identification of plastic types, but at the same time reveals significant limitations of laboratory sorting, especially in the case of heterogeneous mixtures.

3.2.1. Extrusion

Processing the sink fraction (S8, S25) using extruder proved problematic: it was not possible to produce an extrudate suitable for processing. During the extrusion tests, the nozzles repeatedly became clogged and the screw blocked due to fluctuating rheological properties, contamination or varying PC/ABS proportions [15].

Excessive and incompatible PC proportions from WEEE can lead to difficulties in the reproducibility of the melt flow and make extrusion more difficult [15]. According to Pelto et al., the influence on the MFR in recycled PC/ABS blends can result from several factors. The primary reason is considered to be the thermomechanical chain scission of the polycarbonate during previous life cycles and the recycling process. This degradation reduces the average molecular weight, which lowers the melt viscosity and thus increases the MFR. In parallel, residual low-molecular-weight impurities or degradation products of any flame retardants present could influence the flow properties by acting in part as internal plasticisers.

According to Pelto et al., targeted control of the MFR could be achieved through the use of compatibilisers, which modify the interfacial tension between the PC and ABS phases. Whilst the degradation of r-PC tends to increase the MFR, the improved phase bonding achieved through additives or potential chain extension leads to an increase in molecular cross-linking, thereby stabilising the viscosity and controllably reducing the MFR

SEM and EDX analyses of the annealed residue from the clogged filters showed clear Ti and Si compounds. Digital microscope images also documented trapped air bubbles in the sample [16].

Ti and Si compounds are commonly used in electronic components, for example for heat resistance, mechanical robustness, electromagnetic shielding, and UV and weather protection. TiO₂ in particular serves as a white pigment in many plastic components. Further targeted investigations are necessary to clarify the exact causes of the extrusion problems and to optimize possible separation or processing steps [17].

The floating fractions (F8, F25) of the router housings could be successfully extruded (G8, G25). Degassing and temperatures had to be increased slightly to ensure a stable process. Initially, the floating fraction was processed at temperatures typical for ABS, e.g., 200°-250°C. This did not produce any results, as the material was not melted properly. After several readjustments by increasing the processing temperatures up to 220°-285°C. These temperatures are similar to the PC processing temperatures. This also underlines the difficulty of separating the ABS and PC/ABS fractions mentioned in the chapter on separation [18].

3.3. Characterisation

In the following section, the results of the material characterization of the manufactured recyclates and fractions are first compared with each other in order to evaluate the different pre-treatment strategies and determine a best-case scenario. In addition to the granulates G8, G25, and the non-processable S8, the float-sink fractions (F8, F25, S8) and the input materials are also discussed.

This is followed by a comparison of the produced recyclates (G8, G25) with commercially available recyclates (R1, R2).

3.3.1. Granulate

MVR measurements of the granulates (G8, G25) show that the 8 mm separated ground materials have a higher MVR and standard deviation than 25 mm (Fig. 9). Different types of ABS occur in WEEE streams, resulting in a distinctly heterogeneous material composition. This heterogeneity results, among other things, from different polymerization processes, such as bulk polymerization compared to emulsion polymerization, as well as from mixtures with other thermoplastics such as HIPS or PP. In addition, the materials often contain different additives, including flame retardants, fillers, or glass fibers [19].

These structural and chemical differences directly influence the properties of the recycled material obtained from them. In particular, there are significant differences in MVR depending on the respective ABS source. In addition, the varying polymer mixtures result in significant fluctuations in mechanical properties.

Overall, the different ABS compositions result in widely varying material properties of the recyclate [18]. Mechanical recycling (shredding, extrusion) can also promote thermomechanical degradation (chain breakage, oxidation). The aging period of previous use contributes to material heterogeneity [20].

Although the DSC measurements (see Fig.7) show similar curves, they indicate typical ABS or PC behaviour. The glass transitions at approx. 101 °C and 116 °C are comparable. The delta Cp values also show no significant differences. G25 exhibits noticeably higher peaks at 130 °C. G8 shows a clearly flattened curve with two small peaks between 120 and 135°C. GR3 shows a high flattened and shifted curve in the glass transition at 101°C, which suggests a lower ABS content and a higher proportion of PC in the material.

A second glass transition occurs at approximately 150 °C, with a peak at approximately 160 °C. In all the curves shown (F8, F25, S8), two to three glass transitions are visible: Tg1 ~ 101–103 °C (ABS (SAN phase)), Tg2 ~ 116–117 °C (not typical of pure PC, but rather of a PC-influenced ABS phase), Tg3 ~ 150–152 °C (typical PC Tg in DSC), very weak but likely [21].

Figure 7: DSC results for samples G8, G25, and non-process-stable granulate from S8

PC contamination is present in all samples, but differences can be observed that point to the following aspects: in the upper curves (light blue), the PC is very finely dispersed (not visible as a separate phase). In the middle curve (blue), it can be assumed that the PC begins to appear as a separate phase, and in a higher proportion than in the upper curve. In the lower curve (dark blue), the PC is present as a phase [22]. The dark blue curve shows the sinking fraction (S8) with a typical PC curve, which is consistent with the results of the density measurements and the interrupted extrusion processes. The other two curves represent the granulates (G8, G25) from the floating fractions of SF8 and S25. The light blue curve is G8 and, as described above, shows lower PC contamination and thus higher separation efficiency. Studies show that WEEE plastic streams frequently contain mixed engineering polymers and that residual contamination remains even after sorting and recycling. This includes PC components in rABS fractions (Tg signal at ~150 °C)[22].

A comparison of the measured densities of granulates G8 (1.11 g/cm³) and G25 (1.13 g/cm³) (Fig. 8) and the measured density of the floating fraction from 8 and 25 mm (FF2) (ø1.12 g/cm³) shows that these correspond. However, these measured densities are too high for the typical densities of ABS. High-impact, flame-retardant modified ABS can also have higher densities (1.02–1.21 g/cm³) [23], which is another indication that PC/ABS blends may have entered the floating ABS fraction. A strict separation of both (ABS and PC/ABS) components is not possible within the scope of this work and must be further optimized. PC/ABS blends have a density between ABS and pure polycarbonate, as the

higher proportion of the denser PC component increases the overall density [23]. The measured granulate SF G8 (1.27 g/cm) corresponds to a higher proportion of PC/ABS mixture.

Figure 8: Density of different material fractions: FF = floating fraction, SF = sinking fraction

In rPC/rABS blends, a high degree of variability in the melt viscosity ratio can be observed, which is attributable to the different viscosities and impurities of the recycled PC and ABS fractions. The present study shows that uniform melting and stable extrusion are difficult to achieve because the flow conditions vary and the phases are not optimally distributed [17, 14]. It has been found that PC and ABS are fundamentally incompatible or only mixable to a limited extent. The use of inappropriate compatibilizers results in phase-separated melts in which the components do not form a homogeneous melt. This has a negative effect on extrusion pressures, flow, and mechanical properties [23]. Recycled PC and ABS originate from real heterogeneous WEEE waste and vary greatly in composition (additives, ageing, etc.) and probably in molar mass distribution. When the blend contains high proportions of PC, the viscosity in the molten state is significantly higher and more variable, resulting in technical challenges during extrusion and mixing processes (e.g., uneven flow, poor melt mixing, and difficult-to-control process parameters) [15]

3.3.2. Mechanical testing

Tensile tests on the manufactured test specimens (see Fig.9 b-c) provide, among other things, the tensile strength and tensile modulus of elasticity. The tensile strengths of the test bars made of G8 and G25 are presented here. The tensile strength and tensile modulus show no significant differences at 8 and 25 mm. The dispersion for G25 is higher. This indicates increased structural inhomogeneity, presumably caused by PC domains, phase interfaces, and thermally degraded polymer chains, which locally influence crack initiation [18].

Figure 9: Mechanical testing results for the regranulates from the router housings (G8, G25) compared to the commercially available recyclates (R1, R2)

The bending tests on the test specimens produced provide, among other things, the flexural strength and flexural modulus (see Fig. 9 d-e). The test bars made of G25 show slightly higher values, meaning that they are somewhat stiffer and less flexible than the test bars made of G8, which has a higher standard deviation. Higher deviations are due to higher contamination in the mixture [18]. In PC/ABS, the modulus of elasticity generally increases with increasing PC content. This is because PC is stiffer than ABS and – even in the form of dispersed domains – increases the overall stiffness [24]. This indicates that the 25 mm separated fraction produces a lower separation efficiency of PC [22].

Higher flexural moduli in WEEE recyclates often indicate thermally damaged, shorter polymer chains [25, 26].

The measured MVR values are both low. The lower MVR values of the ABS/PC indicate a higher melt viscosity. The granulate, which was previously separated at 8 mm, shows a higher MVR value. ABS recycled plastic from WEEE tends to show an increase in MVR, which indicates that there is a higher ABS content in this fraction and that the separation quality appears to be higher at 8 mm shredding [28, 27].

The simultaneous increase in the flexural modulus observed in G25 could therefore not be attributed to thermal degradation, but rather to a change in morphology or composition. In G25, this indicates a higher PC content [27]. PC acts as the stiff, load-bearing phase, consistent with the lower MVR value. G8 shows a lower flexural modulus but a higher MVR value. The reduced flexural modulus of the ABS/PC blend can be explained consistently with a lower PC content. The higher melt flow rate observed at the same time supports this interpretation, as ABS has a lower melt viscosity than PC.

The results of the mechanical tests indicate that density separation using the float-sink method achieves a higher separation efficiency with 8 mm regrind. The FTIR spectra of the bulk materials proved ABS, the granulate produced showed ABS/PC spectra, but the mechanical values indicate a lower PC content in this fraction.

As part of this study, the input material underwent a multi-stage mechanical preparation and processing route consisting of comminution, separation (magnetic separation and float-sink separation), cleaning, extrusion, and subsequent injection molding. After initial screening and material characterization, different pretreatment strategies and varying process sequences were investigated. The process parameters of the individual stages were systematically varied and evaluated in terms of their influence on recyclate quality using statistical experimental design.

A comparison of the strategies showed that the particle size after shredding has a decisive influence on the efficiency of the subsequent separation steps. The laboratory-scale shredding of router housings with a screen size of 8 mm led

to improved material separation and showed increased separation efficiency in the subsequent magnetic separation and float-sink separation. This process was therefore identified as the most promising route in terms of recyclate quality and formed the basis for further ecological assessment using life cycle analysis (LCA).

3.3.3. Comparison with commercially available recyclates

There are no significant differences in tensile strength between 8 mm and 25 mm. Compared to commercially available materials [3, 4], they prove to be lower (Fig.9) and do not achieve the values of commercially available recyclates. Higher tensile strengths mean higher mechanical load-bearing capacity, lower deformation tendency, and better dimensional stability of the injection-molded part. The tensile modulus reaches higher values for G8 and G25. The flexural modulus of the manufactured recyclates is comparable to that of commercially available recyclates (anjacom no data available). The measurement of the MVR values for G8 shows values that are partly lower but also higher than those of the commercial recyclates. The measurement of sample G25 shows a lower MVR value than both commercially available recyclates, which indicates a higher melt viscosity. The low MVR values do not indicate any significant degradation of the molecular chains, which is advantageous for an ABS/PC recyclate. The low impact strength values [28] (Fig.9) can also be caused by impurities and material dispersion. A comparison of the recyclates produced with commercially available recyclates shows a typical recycling pattern and can be optimized using compatibilizers. Mechanical properties can be specifically improved and enhanced to achieve higher quality.

3.4. Environmental assessment

For the environmental assessment, the recycling approach producing regranulate from the 8 mm fraction ('G8') was assessed since it was considered more promising after characterisation and injection moulding. The mechanical recycling approach is compared to the current waste treatment, incineration with energy recovery (see Fig. 10). All results for the individual impact categories without normalization and weighting are provided in the Supplementary Information.

Figure 10: Environmental impacts (EF 3.1 Single score) for mechanical recycling and incineration with energy recovery of 1 kg of router housings (100%: mechanical recycling impacts) *material credit only applicable with appropriate product application

Incineration has higher impacts, namely 509% of the recycling impacts, but receives credits (-422%) for recovering electricity and heat. In general, it is expected that the credits for energy recovery are going to decrease in the future, when more sustainable energy production processes are substituted. However, currently, incineration has net impacts of 87% of the recycling impacts after totalling the impacts and credits.

On the other hand, the recycling of 1 kg of router housings produces 456 g of regranulate. An environmental credit can be achieved when the recyclate can substitute the same amount of virgin material in a product application similar to the energy credits. In that case, the material credit for avoiding virgin ABS/PC production (-2037%) leads to net-negative environmental impacts for the mechanical recycling approach (-1937%) that are much lower than the net impacts of the incineration process.

The scenario analysis covers two scenarios with decreased and increased energy efficiency of the sink-float separation, the results are provided in Figure 11. Two sink-float separation processes are included in the mechanical recycling approach and changes in their energy demand also affect the overall environmental impacts. In the assessed scenarios, the Single score results vary from 435% of the base scenario result for a lower energy efficiency and 97% for the higher energy efficiency. On one hand, this highlights the importance of a precise data collection process. On the other hand, it illustrates that even while the impacts of the recycling process may vary depending on process configurations, the

potential credit for substituting virgin material may still lead to overall net-negative environmental impacts for the recycling approach.

Figure 11 Environmental impacts (EF 3.1 Single score) of the mechanical recycling approach using a scenario analysis for different energy efficiencies of the sink-float separation

3.5. Limitations

Regarding the environmental impacts, in this study, the mechanical properties of the recycled material were only compared to other recyclates. Therefore, without a product application, no statements on the substitution potential for virgin ABS/PC and therefore the actual environmental benefits are possible. However, since the recyclates are commercially available, the authors assume a market demand for them. Also, the LCA results were calculated from a mix of available lab-scale and semi-industrial scale data and literature data. The scenario analysis illustrates how this influences the potential environmental impacts. The model used for the calculations represents the status quo of the recycling approach. Future implementation on a larger scale may result in different results due to an increased efficiency or different configurations of the modelled processes.

4. Conclusions

The present study demonstrates that the production of recycled material from WEEE-derived router housings is technically feasible and, from a resource perspective, justified. However, efficient material recovery is challenged by the heterogeneous composition of the input stream and the varying polymer contents within the individual components. FTIR analyses suggest a theoretical separation into ABS and PC/ABS fractions. In practice, the float-sink separation resulted in a floating fraction predominantly consisting of ABS with minor PC content and a sinking fraction characterized by a significantly higher PC proportion. The floating fraction proved to be processable by extrusion, which, in agreement with experimental results and literature data, indicates a comparatively low PC content. In contrast, the sinking fraction was not extrudable under the investigated processing conditions, suggesting a substantially higher PC content. The results further underline that the particle size after pre-treatment significantly influences separation efficiency. In particular, the laboratory-scale shredding with an 8 mm screen size improved material liberation and enhanced the separation performance of subsequent processing steps, contributing to the identification of the most promising route in terms of recyclate quality.

Due to the limited inherent compatibility between PC and ABS, the heterogeneity of WEEE recyclates further aggravates phase separation during melt processing. Without the use of suitable compatibilizers, the formation of a stable and homogeneous melt is not achievable, thereby limiting the direct mechanical recycling of mixed PC/ABS-rich fractions.

The sink fraction should be investigated further, as SI compounds prevent extrusion. Further investigations are needed to determine whether melt filters can be used to obtain a processable fraction. The sorting process should be optimized and tested on a large scale. The process should take into account the quality of the recyclate and the effectiveness of the processing. At this point, attention should also be paid to compatibility issues in the mixture.

Supplementary Information

Yasemin Celik*, Meret Jürgens, Niklas Rode, Madina Shamsuyeva, Hans-Josef Endres

Institute of Plastics and Circular Economy, Leibniz Universität Hannover, An der Universität 2, 30823 Garbsen, Germany

* Corresponding author. *E-mail address:* celik@ikk.uni-hannover.de

A. Life Cycle Inventory

The life cycle inventories are listed in *Table Conclusions.1* to *Table Conclusions.9*. The following general assumptions were applied:

- Electricity is supplied by the general German electricity mix (2022). Process water supply is modelled as tap water from groundwater.
- Residual waste is treated as commercial waste. For plastic residues, the process 'DE: Plastics (unspecified) in waste incineration plant (14.4% H₂O content)' was applied including credits for energy recovery. For all other residues, the process 'DE: Commercial waste in municipal waste incineration plant (0% H₂O content)' was applied including credits for energy recovery.
- For the float-sink-separation, it was assumed that around 5.5 kg of water are required per 1 kg of treated waste according to process estimations that align with literature values [5]. Since most of the water is reused, it was assumed that only 3 % of the required water is supplied from freshwater to account for the less frequent total water exchanges. The same assumptions on water consumption were used for the washing processes.
- No primary data was available for the granulation of the extrudate. Therefore, datasets were used to account for the granulation process.
- As the processes of washing and drying were carried out manually, no energy consumption data was recorded. Therefore, to account for this thermal and electrical energy consumption on industrial scale, data from Larrain et al. [5] was used.
- Transport processes were not considered, as it was assumed that all recycling processes would be combined at the same location.
- For reference, the environmental impacts were compared to virgin material and an alternative disposal route. It was assumed that granulate from the floating fraction would replace a blend with 65wt.% ABS and 35wt.% PC. Virgin material was modelled using the 'DE: Acrylonitrile-butadiene-styrene granulate (ABS) mix' and 'DE: Polycarbonate granulate (PC)' processes.
- For the alternative disposal route, it was assumed that the waste stream would usually be incinerated in Germany with energy recovery. This was modelled using the same processes as the ones used for the residual waste including credits for energy recovery.

Table Conclusions.1: Life cycle inventory for the pre-grinding (2-shaft shredder)

Pre-grinding (2-shaft shredder)				
Inputs	Amount	Unit	Note	Dataset
Waste stream (router housings)	7.70	kg	No burdens (cut-off)	–
Electricity	5.50	MJ		DE: Electricity grid mix (2022) 1,54kwh
Outputs	Amount	Unit	Note	Dataset
Router housings (shredded)	7.10	kg		–
Residual waste	0.60	kg	Commercial waste (metals, rubber, other residues)	DE: Commercial waste in municipal waste incineration plant (0% H ₂ O content)

Table Conclusions.2: Life cycle inventory for the magnetic separator

Magnetic separator				
Inputs	Amount	Unit	Note	Dataset
Router housings (shredded)	7.70	kg	–	–
Electricity	0.1	MJ	–	DE: Electricity grid mix (2022)
Outputs	Amount	Unit	Note	Dataset
Non-magnetic fraction	7.10	kg	–	–
Residual waste	0.60	kg	Commercial waste (metals, rubber, other residues)	DE: Commercial waste in municipal waste incineration plant (0% H ₂ O content)

Table Conclusions.3: Life cycle inventory for the float-sink separation (water)

Float-sink-separation (water, 1.0 g/cm ³)				
Inputs	Amount	Unit	Note	Dataset
Non-magnetic fraction	10.00	kg		–
Electricity	0.15	kWh	Data tested in a sensitivity analysis	DE: Electricity grid mix (2022)
Water	1.65	kg	Assumption (3 % of required amount)	DE: Tap water from groundwater
Outputs	Amount	Unit	Note	Dataset
Fraction for further use	9.00	kg	–	–
Residual waste	1.00	kg	Commercial waste (plastics)	DE: Plastics (unspecified) in waste incineration plant (14.4% H ₂ O content)
Wastewater	1.65	kg	Assumption (3 % of required amount)	DE: Municipal wastewater treatment (mix)

Table Conclusions.4: Life cycle inventory for the float-sink-separation (salt)

Float-sink-separation (salt, 1.1 g/cm ³)				
Inputs	Amount	Unit	Note	Dataset
Fraction for further use	9.00	kg	–	–
Electricity	0.15	kWh	Data tested in a sensitivity analysis	DE: Electricity grid mix (2022)
Water	1.34	kg	Assumption (3 % of required amount)	DE: Tap water from groundwater
Salt	0.15	kg	–	DE: Sodium chloride (rock salt)
Outputs	Amount	Unit	Note	Dataset
Floating fraction	6.00	kg	–	–
Sinking fraction	3.00	kg	To waste (cannot be processed)	DE: Plastics (unspecified) in waste incineration plant (14.4% H ₂ O content)
Wastewater	1.49	kg	Assumption (3 % of required amount)	DE: Municipal wastewater treatment (mix)

Table Conclusions.5: Life cycle inventory for washing

Washing				
Inputs	Amount	Unit	Note	Dataset
Floating fraction	6.00	kg	–	–
Water	0.99	kg	Same assumption as for the float-sink-separation (3 % of required amount)	DE: Tap water from groundwater
Electricity	0.173	kWh	Literature data [5]	DE: Electricity grid mix (2022)
Outputs	Amount	Unit	Note	Dataset
Washed floating fraction	6.00	kg	–	–
Wastewater	0.99	kg	Same assumption as for the float-sink-separation (3 % of required amount)	DE: Municipal wastewater treatment (mix)

Table Conclusions.6: Life cycle inventory for the drying

Drying				
Inputs	Amount	Unit	Note	Dataset
Washed floating fraction	1.00	t	-	-
Electricity	18.20	kWh	Literature data [5]	DE: Electricity grid mix (2022)
Thermal Energy	25.80	kWh	Literature data [5]	DE: Thermal energy mix (2021)
Outputs	Amount	Unit	Note	Dataset
Dried floating fraction	1.00	t	-	-

Table Conclusions.7: Life cycle inventory for shredding (4 mm)

Shredding (4 mm)				
Inputs	Amount	Unit	Note	Dataset
Dried floating fraction	6.00	kg	-	-
Electricity	5.30	MJ		DE: Electricity grid mix (2022)
Outputs	Amount	Unit	Note	Dataset
Shredded floating fraction	6.00	kg	-	-

Table Conclusions.8: Life cycle inventory for extrusion

Extrusion				
Inputs	Amount	Unit	Note	Dataset
Shredded floating fraction	6.00	kg	-	-
Electricity	2.52	MJ	-	DE: Electricity grid mix (2022)
Outputs	Amount	Unit	Note	Dataset
Extrudate I	5.64	kg	To replace ABS/PC	-
Material losses	0.36	kg	Assumption: 6 % losses	DE: Plastics (unspecified) in waste incineration plant (14.4% H2O content)

Table Conclusions.9: Life cycle inventory for the granulation

Granulation				
Inputs	Amount	Unit	Note	Dataset
Extrudate I	1.00	kg	-	-
Granulation	1.00	kg	No primary data	DE: Granulator (30-1500 kg/h throughput)
Outputs	Amount	Unit	Note	Dataset
Granulate I (recycled)	1.00	kg	To replace ABS/PC	-

B. Life Cycle Impact Assessment (LCIA)

The results of the life cycle impact assessment are listed in *Table Conclusions.10*. The normalized and weighted Single Score results are presented alongside the individual impact category results. The results are scaled to the results of the developed recycling approach (100%) for data confidentiality reasons.

Table Conclusions.10: Results of the life cycle impact assessment for the respective reference flow; for data confidentiality reasons, all results are scaled to the results of the developed recycling approach (100%)

Impact category	Unit	Recycling approach	Material credit for substitution of virgin ABS/PC (negative)	Incineration	Energy credit for substitution energy production (negative)
Reference flow		1 kg of waste	mass of produced recyclate	1 kg of waste	amount of produced energy
Acidification	mol H+ eq	100%	-2660 %	390 %	-1337 %
Climate Change	kg CO2 eq	100%	-262 %	384 %	-179 %
Ecotoxicity, freshwater	CTUe	100%	8188 %	-106 %	729 %
Eutrophication, freshwater	kg P eq	100%	-2087 %	56 %	-870 %
Eutrophication, marine	kg N eq	100%	-3448 %	333 %	-1693 %
Eutrophication, terr.	mol N eq	100%	-1572 %	297 %	-813 %
Human toxicity, cancer	CTUh	100%	50013 %	-1664 %	7725 %
Human toxicity, non-cancer	CTUh	100%	-3342 %	1086 %	-1928 %
Ionising radiation	kBq U235	100%	-2616 %	233 %	-3484 %
Land Use	pt	100%	243 %	-27 %	562 %
Ozone depletion	kg CFC-11 eq	100%	-1932 %	227 %	-3407 %
Particulate matter	disease incidences	100%	-7128 %	1519 %	-3512 %
Photochemical ozone formation	kg NMVOC eq	100%	-6126 %	470 %	-2169 %
Resource use, fossils	MJ	100%	1225 %	-39 %	476 %
Resource use, mineral and metals	kg Sb eq	100%	4455 %	-255 %	3470 %
Water use	m3 world eq	100%	-81 %	215 %	-13 %
Single Score	-	100%	-879 %	509 %	-422 %

The normalised results (in %) for material and energy credit are positive in some impact categories, which may seem counterintuitive at first glance. This is because the developed recycling approach generates waste that is incinerated. The energy produced during this incineration is credited when modelling the recycling approach. In some impact categories, this credit is higher than the impacts for energy and water consumed by the recycling approach. As a result, the numerical results for the recycling approach, which are used as a reference (as '100%'), are negative in some impact categories. Since the numerical results for material and energy credit are also negative (i.e. the same negative sign as for the recycling approach), the normalised results (in %) become positive in these impact categories, even though a credit is represented.

C. Scenario analysis

To assess the influence of individual data points, a scenario analysis was carried out for the electricity consumption of the float-sink-separation. Different data was available and is listed in *Table Conclusions.11*, the results are listed in *Table Conclusions.12*.

Table Conclusions.11: Data used for the scenario analysis on the electricity consumption of the float-sink-separation

Scenario	Scale	Description	Electricity consumption (kWh/kg input)	Data used for sensitivity analysis (kWh/kg input)
Scenario 1 (low efficiency)	Lab	Results from own lab-scale test with an energy consumption of 0.4-0.6 kWh per test and throughput of 0.5-0.6 kg material per test	0.67-1.20	1.2
Base scenario	Industrial	Information on industrial scale of the same separation unit by the manufacturer with an energy consumption of 3-15 kWh/t [29]	0.003-0.015	0.015
Scenario 2 (high efficiency)	Industrial (standardized process)	Literature data [5]	0.0035	0.0035

Table Conclusions.12: Results (EF 3.1 method) of the scenario analysis for the recycling of 1 kg of waste, all results are scaled to the results of the base scenario (100%)

Impact category	Unit	Scenario 1 (low efficiency)	Base scenario	Scenario 2 (high efficiency)
Acidification	mol H+ eq	1443%	100%	86%
Climate Change	kg CO2 eq	234%	100%	99%
Ecotoxicity, freshwater	CTUe	-596%	100%	107%
Eutrophication, freshwater	kg P eq	1284%	100%	88%
Eutrophication, marine	kg N eq	1675%	100%	84%
Eutrophication, terr.	mol N eq	854%	100%	92%
Human toxicity, cancer	CTUh	-10111%	100%	203%
Human toxicity, non-cancer	CTUh	2402%	100%	77%
Ionising radiation	kBq U235	6279%	100%	37%
Land Use	pt	-411%	100%	105%
Ozone depletion	kg CFC-11 eq	6160%	100%	39%
Particulate matter	disease incidences	3675%	100%	64%
Photochem. ozone formation	kg NMVOC eq	1913%	100%	82%
Resource use, fossils	MJ	-253%	100%	104%
Resource use, mineral and metals	kg Sb eq	-5174%	100%	153%
Water use	m3 world eq	120%	100%	100%
Single Score	-	437%	100%	97%

Author contributions

Yasemin Celik: Project administration, Conceptualization, Writing–original draft, Investigation. Meret Jürgens: Investigation, Methodology, Visualization, Writing–original draft, Niklas Rode: Project administration, Investigation. Madina Shamsuyeva: Funding acquisition, Supervision, Writing – review & editing. Hans-Josef Endres: Supervision

Funding sources

This work was financially supported by the Ministry of Science and Culture (MWK) of Lower Saxony as a part of the grant number ZN 4173 for the project ReKon – Recycling concepts for high-quality mechanical recycling of previously non-recyclable waste streams of technical plastic components from the mobility, energy, electronic and electrical equipment (E&E) and health/pharmaceutical sectors.

Conflicts of interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

Acknowledgements

The authors acknowledge Electrocyling GmbH for supplying the router housings used in this study.

Data availability

The data supporting this article have been included as part of the Supplementary Information.

References

1. Lindner C, Arnold M, Hein J (2025) Status quo und Prognose des Bedarfs und der Verfügbarkeit von Post-Consumer-Rezyklaten im Jahr 2030
2. van der Vegt M, Velzing E-J, Rietbergen M et al. (2022) Understanding Business Requirements for Increasing the Uptake of Recycled Plastic: A Value Chain Perspective. Recycling 7. <https://doi.org/10.3390/recycling7040042>
3. almaak international GmbH Anjacom PC/ABS R050/75S: unreinforced, recycling grade, recycelat, black 91012. <https://almaak.de/en/products/datasheet/>. Accessed 29 Jan 2026
4. ALBIS Distribution GmbH und Co. KG (2022) Altech PC+ABS ECO 1000/568. <https://www.albis.com/en/products/download/doc/en/SI/albis/ALTECHPCABSECO1000568.pdf>. Accessed 29 Jan 2026

5. Larrain M, van Passel S, Thomassen G et al. (2021) Techno-economic assessment of mechanical recycling of challenging post-consumer plastic packaging waste. *Resources, Conservation and Recycling* 170:105607. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.resconrec.2021.105607>
6. Andreasi Bassi S, Biganzoli F, Ferrara N et al. (2023) Updated characterisation and normalisation factors for the Environmental Footprint 3.1 method. JRC Technical Report, Luxembourg
7. Bano S, Iqbal T, Ramzan N et al. (2021) Study of Surface Mechanical Characteristics of ABS/PC Blends Using Nanoindentation. *Processes* 9:637. <https://doi.org/10.3390/pr9040637>
8. Shijie Wu, Yao Fu, Soham Das, Miles Pamueles Duan, Tan Zhang Synthesis of Acrylonitrile-Butadiene-Styrene Copolymers Through Interface-Initiated Room-Temperature Polymerization: Synthesis of Acrylonitrile-Butadiene-Styrene Copolymers Through Interface-Initiated Room-Temperature Polymerization Shijie Wu, Yao Fu, Soham Das, Miles Pamueles Duan, Tan Zhang* Division of Natural and Applied Sciences, Duke Kunshan University, Kunshan, Jiangsu 215316, China Supporting Information Electronic Supplementary Material (ESI) for Reaction Chemistry & Engineering
9. Wu S, Fu Y, Das S et al. (2024) Synthesis of acrylonitrile–butadiene–styrene copolymers through interface-initiated room-temperature polymerization. *React Chem Eng* 9:2282–2292. <https://doi.org/10.1039/d4re00152d>
10. Martinho G, Pires A, Saraiva L et al. (2012) Composition of plastics from waste electrical and electronic equipment (WEEE) by direct sampling. *Waste Manag* 32:1213–1217. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.wasman.2012.02.010>
11. Orzan E, Janewithayapun R, Gutkin R et al. (2021) Thermo-mechanical variability of post-industrial and post-consumer recycle PC-ABS. *Polymer Testing* 99:107216. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.polymertesting.2021.107216>
12. Päivi Fjäder, Topi Turunen, Petra Rinne, Eevaleena Häkkinen, Sari Kauppi, Tuomas Sormunen, Mirja Andersson Harmful additives in WEEE plastics and the regulatory framework:25–71
13. Bauer M, Lehner M, Schwabl D et al. (2018) Sink–float density separation of post-consumer plastics for feedstock recycling. *J Mater Cycles Waste Manag* 20:1781–1791. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10163-018-0748-z>
14. Pelto J, Barreto C, Anwar H et al. (2023) Compatibilized PC/ABS blends from solvent recycled PC and ABS polymers from electronic equipment waste. *Polymer Testing* 120:107969. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.polymertesting.2023.107969>
15. Arnold JC, Alston S, Holder A (2009) Void formation due to gas evolution during the recycling of Acrylonitrile–Butadiene–Styrene copolymer (ABS) from waste electrical and electronic equipment (WEEE). *Polymer Degradation and Stability* 94:693–700. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.polymdegradstab.2008.12.019>
16. Bill A, Haarman A, Gasser M et al. (2022) Characterizing plastics from large household appliances: Brominated flame retardants, other additives and density profiles. *Resources, Conservation and Recycling* 177:105956. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.resconrec.2021.105956>
17. Lesiak A, Vincent L, Schollaert J et al. (2025) Effect of mechanical recycling and virgin PBR addition on the properties of ABS recovered from WEEE: A multi-technique characterization. *Waste Management Bulletin* 3:100238. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.wmb.2025.100238>
18. Munshi GA, Kulkarni VM (2025) A comprehensive study on restoring properties in expired/aged ABS materials: advanced techniques, additive integration and challenges for sustainable industrial reuse and manufacturing. *J Mater Sci: Mater Eng* 20. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40712-025-00260-5>
19. Bulanda K, Oleksy M, Oliwa R (2023) Polymer Composites Based on Polycarbonate/Acrylonitrile-Butadiene-Styrene Used in Rapid Prototyping Technology. *Polymers (Basel)* 15. <https://doi.org/10.3390/polym15061565>
20. Schlummer M, Wolff F, Maurer A Recovery of PC/ABS from WEEE plastic shred by the CreaSolv® process:1–6. <https://doi.org/10.1109/EGG.2016.7829841>

21. Jung SM (2025) Recent Progress in Sustainable Recycling of Waste Acrylonitrile–Butadiene–Styrene (ABS) Plastics. *Sustainability* 17:8742. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su17198742>
22. Wagner F, Peeters JR, Ramon H et al. (2020) Quality assessment of mixed plastic flakes from Waste Electrical and Electronic Equipment (WEEE) by spectroscopic techniques. *Resources, Conservation and Recycling* 158:104801. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.resconrec.2020.104801>
23. Krache R, Debah I (2011) Some Mechanical and Thermal Properties of PC/ABS Blends. *MSA* 02:404–410. <https://doi.org/10.4236/msa.2011.25052>
24. Balart R, López J, García D et al. (2005) Recycling of ABS and PC from electrical and electronic waste. Effect of miscibility and previous degradation on final performance of industrial blends. *European Polymer Journal* 41:2150–2160. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eurpolymj.2005.04.001>
25. Ventosinos Louzao V, García Murias D, Dios Álvarez MÁ de et al. (2024) Impact of recyclability on the tensile and Impact properties of coated plastic materials for the automotive and electronic sectors. *Open Res Eur* 4:51. <https://doi.org/10.12688/openreseurope.16888.4>
26. Zanatta S, Boaretti C, Dal Lago E et al. (2024) Mechanical Recycling of Post-Industrial PC/ABS Blends from the Automotive Sector by Mixture Design. *Processes* 12:349. <https://doi.org/10.3390/pr12020349>